

Thick then thin – a novel approach to reducing plant spacing variability in small-seeded vegetable crops

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Abstract

Establishment outcomes can be highly variable in small-seeded vegetable crops, reducing crop value through lower yields and higher product variability. We conducted a proof-of-concept study to explore the potential to achieve targeted plant populations consistently and to reduce variability in plant spacing by sowing additional seed and thinning emerged plants. In one onion crop, replicated plots were sown at half the standard within-row plant spacing (72 mm). Eight weeks after sowing, plant spacing was recorded in each plot, and then thinned using templates that identified plants to be removed based on spacing from the last retained plant (plant distance thinning), or at fixed distances from the start of the plot (fixed distance thinning). Plant-distance thinning treatments reduced within-row spacing variability (coefficient of variation (CV) 75% pre-thinning to 34% post-thinning). The mean spacing (74 mm) was similar to that of the control plots (73 mm; CV 61%). Fixed-distance thinning treatments increased the mean and CV to 115 mm and 84% respectively. A survey of six commercial onion fields showed that they varied significantly in within-row plant spacing variance (< 0.001). Sowing more thickly, and then thinning small-seeded crops like onions shows promise in reducing plant spacing variability, extending the existing use of this approach from crops such as lettuce where automated thinning is being developed. The next consideration is measuring the impact of thinning treatments on yield and variability and considering automated methods for thinning of tightly spaced crops.

Background

Establishment of small-seeded vegetable crops can be highly variable, reducing crop value through lower yield and higher product variability. One strategy employed to reduce interplant spacing variability in lettuce is planting additional seed followed by selective thinning manually or with automated thinning equipment (Chu et al. 2016; Mosqueda et al. 2017).

To our knowledge this has not been attempted with vegetable crops that have a high planting density and are subject to significant variation in establishment and resulting plant population within a field (Chuet al. 2016; Mosqueda et al. 2017). We conducted a proof-of-concept study to explore the potential to achieve targeted plant populations consistently and to reduce variability in plant spacing by sowing additional seed and thinning emerged plants. We did this in a commercial onion crop which typically has a within-row spacing one tenth of the plant spacing in head lettuce crops, where this concept has been developed. Onion establishment is often highly variable because of factors such as small seed size, high genetic variability and planting during cold/wet conditions (Brewster 2008). Poor establishment of onion crops has been strongly linked to low onion crop yields and variability in bulb size (Bleasdale 1966; Searle et al. 2014). Achieving a more uniform plant spacing across a field has potential for improving yield and product uniformity for growers of small-seeded vegetable crops.

Methods

In a commercial onion crop near Hastings, New Zealand, replicated plots were sown thickly at a within-row spacing of 36 mm, which is half the standard within-row plant spacing of 72 mm. Once plants were at the two-leaf stage (eight weeks after sowing), plant spacing was recorded in each 3 m by 1 m bed plot (8 rows), and then thinned using templates that identified plants to be removed based on spacing from the last retained plant (plant distance thinning, PDT), or on fixed distances from the start of the plot (fixed distance thinning, FDT). In each replicate there was a control plot with seed planted at the standard spacing. There were three replicates per treatment.

In addition to the plant spacing in the experiment crop, measurements were taken in six additional commercial onion crops to benchmark within-row spacing uniformity. Three replicate plots of the same size were assessed at each survey site.

Homogeneity of variance in within row plant spacing among treatments and among survey field sites tested using Levene's test. We used R (version 3.4).

Results

The PDT treatments reduced within-row spacing variability from a coefficient of variation (CV) of 75% pre-thinning to 34% post-thinning. The mean spacing (74 mm) was similar to that of the control plots (73 mm), which had a CV of 61%. FDT treatments increased the mean and CV of within-row spacing to 115 mm and 84% respectively (Table 1).

Table 1. Within-row plant spacing (mm) of treatment onion plots. Treatment plots were 3 m long by 1 bed wide, replicated three times. Fixed distance thinning (FDT), Plant distance thinning (PDT), standard deviation (SD), and coefficient of variation (CV).

Treatments	Mean	Median	SD.	CV%
Control	73.3	70	44.4	60.6
FDT	115.3	80	96.6	83.8
PDT	73.8	70	24.8	33.6
P-value			< 0.001	

The distribution of plant spacing differed amongst treatments. The spread of planting spacing was wide and flat for the control treatment, the FDT treatment showed three peaks at approximately 70-mm intervals, while PDT showed one clear peak at 73 mm (Figure 1). This confirms that a greater proportion of plants were close to the mean spacing in the PDT treatment than in the control or FDT treatments.

Figure 1. Distribution of within-row onion plant spacing (mm) at the thinning experiment site. Treatment plots were 3 m long by 1 bed wide, replicated three times. Fixed distance thinning (FDT), Plant distance thinning (PDT).

Distribution of within-row spacing from the commercial crop survey showed a range of patterns, some of which were similar to the control treatment in the experiment (Figure 2). In most sites surveyed, this degree of variability of within-row plant spacing was similar to that in the control treatment in the thinning experiment (Table 2).

Table 2. Within-row plant spacing (mm) of from the six commercial onion field survey sites. Three plots of 3 m by one bed assessed at each site. Standard deviation (SD), and coefficient of variation (CV).

Survey sites	Mean	Median	SD.	CV%
A	77.1	70	33.1	43
B	83.9	70	47.9	57
C	83.8	70	51.3	61
D	107.6	100	66.4	62
E	76.4	70	50.8	66
F	85.4	70	62.1	73
P-value	< 0.001			

Figure 2; Distribution of within-row plant spacing (mm) from the six commercial onion field survey sites. Three plots of 3 m by one bed assessed at each site.

Initially yield and quality measurements were planned for the experimental site. Unfortunately the plots were compromised by factors unrelated to the treatments such as unscheduled mechanical lifting, so accurate yield and bulb size assessments could not be completed.

Discussion

Sowing more thickly, and then thinning small-seeded crops like onions showed promise in reducing plant spacing variability, extending the existing use of this approach from crops such as lettuce, where automated thinning is being developed. The within-row spacing variability recorded in the survey of

commercial fields supports the proposition that despite the use of precision sowing equipment such as vacuum plate seeders, the distribution of within-row seed spacing remains high. The next considerations are automated methods to thin tightly spaced crops, and minimise the impact of thinning on retained plants. Although this work focused on the reduction in within-row seed spacing variability, another source of variability that could be used either separately or integrated with plant spacing is vigour, as this has also been observed to vary considerably within some crops. Thinning based on vigour would require a method to quantify vigour rapidly and potentially to rank vigour relative to other plants in the crop before making thinning decisions.

Conclusion

Reducing within-row planting spacing followed by thinning based on the distance between plants shows potential to increase spacing uniformity within small-seeded vegetable crops.

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References

- Bleasdale JKA 1966. The effects of plant spacing on the yield of bulb onions (*Allium Cep A L.*) grown from seed. *Journal of Horticultural Science* 41(2): 145–153.
- Brewster JL 2008. Onions and other vegetable alliums. CABI.
- Chu Q, Liu J, Bali K, Thorp KR, Smith R, Wang G 2016. Automated thinning increases uniformity of in-row spacing and plant size in Romaine Lettuce. *HortTechnology* 26(1): 12–19.
- Mosqueda E, Smith R, Goorahoo D, Shrestha A 2017. Automated lettuce thinners reduce labor requirements and increase speed of thinning. *California Agriculture*. Pp. 1–6.
- Searle B, Johnstone P, Reid J 2014. Aspects of production affecting variability in vegetable crop quality. *Acta Hort.* (ISHS) 1123: 17–26.